

Supplementary Material for the Publication “Towards Personalized Explanations for AI Systems: Designing a Role Model for Explainable AI in Auditing”

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1 Supplementary Material for the Systematic Literature Review

The following search string was used:

(Roles OR Stakeholder) AND (“Explainable Artificial Intelligence” OR (“Artificial Intelligence” AND “XAI”))

The following nine online databases were searched:

- ACM Digital Library (<https://dl.acm.org/>)
- AIS Electronic Library (<https://aisel.aisnet.org/>)
- EBSCO Host (<https://search.ebscohost.com>)
- Emerald Insight (<https://www.emerald.com/insight/>)
- IEEE Xplore (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>)
- Science Direct (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>)
- Springer Link (<https://link.springer.com/>)
- Web of Science (<https://webofscience.com/>)
- Wiley Online Library (<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/>)

Finally, the search yielded in 63 relevant publications. These publications were analysed towards different roles, that have to be considered when designing XAI systems using a concept matrix approach. The final concept matrix is illustrated in the following three pages:

2 Concept Matrix

Table 1. Explainable AI Role Model Concept Matrix

Source	AI Researcher	Data Provider	Data Subject	Decision Subject	Developer	End User	Ethicist	Investor	Legislator	Manager	Public	Regulator
[1]									X			X
[2]			X		X	X		X				
[3]	X				X	X				X		
[4]			X	X	X					X		X
[5]					X	X			X	X		X
[6]	X				X	X			X	X		X
[7]	X				X	X		X	X	X		X
[8]	X				X	X			X	X		X
[9]											X	
[10]	X	X				X		X		X		
[11]		X	X	X	X	X				X		X
[12]	X		X		X	X				X		
[13]				X	X	X		X		X		
[14]										X		
[15]					X	X				X		X
[16]						X				X		
[17]						X						X
[18]	X					X				X		
[19]	X				X	X				X		

Source	AI Researcher	Data Provider	Data Subject	Decision Subject	Developer	End User	Ethicist	Investor	Legislator	Manager	Public	Regulator
[20]	X				X	X				X		X
[21]	X			X	X				X	X		
[22]					X	X				X		
[23]			X		X	X		X				
[24]					X	X						
[25]			X		X	X			X	X		X
[26]	X							X				
[27]	X				X	X			X	X		X
[28]					X					X		
[29]			X	X		X		X				X
[30]					X	X		X		X		
[31]				X	X	X						
[32]	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	
[33]					X	X		X	X	X		X
[34]	X				X	X						
[35]						X						
[36]	X				X	X				X		
[37]				X	X	X						X
[38]					X	X				X		X
[39]						X						
[40]					X	X						
[41]			X		X	X		X		X		X
[42]					X	X		X		X	X	X
[43]					X	X			X	X		X
[44]				X		X				X		X
[45]	X	X	X		X	X	X			X		X

Source	AI Researcher	Data Provider	Data Subject	Decision Subject	Developer	End User	Ethicist	Investor	Legislator	Manager	Public	Regulator
[46]			X		X				X			X
[47]									X			X
[48]					X	X				X		
[49]	X				X	X				X		
[50]					X	X				X		
[51]	X					X				X		
[52]			X		X	X						
[53]						X				X		
[54]	X				X	X						
[55]					X	X						X
[56]	X							X	X			
[57]						X						
[58]						X						X
[59]						X						
[60]					X	X				X		
[61]						X				X		
[62]	X				X	X			X	X		
[63]					X	X				X		
Sum	21	4	12	9	43	53	2	12	15	49	3	25

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